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Samarqand viloyati vrachlar uyushmasi raisi.
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TAHRIRIYAT A'ZOLARI:

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*O'zbekiston Respublikasi Fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
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*Rossiya fanlar akademiyasining akademigi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, A.N. Bakuleva nomidagi yurak-qon tomir jarrohligi ilmiy markazi prezidenti (Moskva)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6180-2619>*

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*Katovitsadagi Sileziya Tibbiyot Universiteti, Yuqori Sileziya Kardiologiya Markazi kardiologiya kafedrasini professori (Polsha)
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Pokushalov Evgeniy Anatolevich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "Yangi tibbiy texnologiyalar markazi" (YTTM) klinik tarmog'ining ilmiy ishlar va rivojlanish bo'yicha bosh direktorining o'rinbosari (Novosibirsk) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich

tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, "akad V. Vohidov nomidagi RIJM davlat muassasasi" bo'limi boshlig'i" <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

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tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Tibbiyot xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini oshirish markazi direktori (Toshkent)

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*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor, Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti rektori
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*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent, Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universitetining fan va innovatsiyalar bo'yicha prorektori (Samarqand)
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Jan Kovak

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*tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professori I.M. Sechenov nomidagi Birinchi Moskva Davlat tibbiyot universiteti (Moskva)
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Trigulova Raisa Xusainovna

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Chief Editor:

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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Department of Internal Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State Medical University, Chairman of the Association of Physicians of the Samarkand Region.
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5705-4972>

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0812-6113>

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2560-5167>

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Zufarov Mirjamol Mirumarovich

Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Head of the Department of the State Institution "RSNPMTSH named after acad. V. Vakhidov"
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4822-3193>

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8040-3704>

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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the Laboratory of Preventive Cardiology, Leading Researcher of the Laboratory of IHD and Atherosclerosis. Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Cardiology (Tashkent) ORCID- 0000-0003-4339-0670

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Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Agababyan Irina Rubenovna
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent,
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tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor,
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ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini mudiri
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Alimov Doniyor Anvarovich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Director of
the Republican Scientific Center of
Emergency Medical Care

Yangiev Bakhtiyor Axmedovich
PhD, Director of Samarkand branch of
the Republican Scientific Center of
Emergency Medical Care

Abdullaev Akbar Xatamovich
Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Chief Researcher of the State Institution
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Practical Medical Center for Therapy and
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<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1766-4458>

Agababyan Irina Rubenovna
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Samarkand State Medical Institute

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Doctor of Medical Sciences, Head of the
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Kamalov Zaynitdin Sayfutdinovich
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for the development of professional
qualifications
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Khusinova Shoira Akbarovna
PhD, Associate Professor, Head of the
Department of General Practice,
Family Medicine FAGE of the
Samarkand State Medical Institute

Shodikulova Gulandom Zikriyaeвна
Doctor of Medical Sciences, professor,
head of the Department of Internal
Diseases N 3 of Samarkand state medical
institute (Samarkand)
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2679-1296>

Халиков Каххор Мирзаевич
кандидат медицинских наук, доцент
заведующий кафедрой биологической
химии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского
университета

Аннаев Музаффар
Ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней и кардиологии №2
Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
(технический секретарь)

Тулабаева Гавхар Миракбаровна
Заведующая кафедрой кардиологии,
Центр развития профессиональной
квалификации медицинских
работников, д.м.н., профессор

**Абдумаджидов Хамидулла
Амануллаевич**
Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу
Али ибн Сино. Кафедра «Хирургические
болезни и реанимация». Доктор
медицинских наук, профессор.

Саидов Максуд Арифович
к.м.н., директор Самаркандского
областного отделения
Республиканского специализированного
научно-практического медицинского
центра кардиологии (г. Самарканд)

Насирова Зарина Акбаровна
PhD, ассистент кафедры внутренних
болезней №2 Самаркандского
Государственного Медицинского
университета (ответственный
секретарь)

Xalikov Qaxxor Mirzayevich
Tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Biologik kimyo kafedrasini mudiri

Annayev Muzaffar G'iyos o'g'li
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti 2-son
ichki kasalliklar va kardiologiya kafedrasini
assistenti (texnik kotib)

Tulabayeva Gavxar Mirakbarovna
kardiologiya kafedrasini mudiri, tibbiyot
xodimlarining kasbiy malakasini rivojlantirish
markazi, tibbiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abdumadjidov Xamidulla Amanullayevich
«Abu Ali ibn Sino nomidagi Buxoro davlat
tibbiyot oliygohi» Xirurgiya kasalliklari va
reanimatsiya kafedrasini professori, tibbiyot
fanlari doktori.

Saidov Maqsud Arifovich
tibbiyot fanlari nomzodi,
Respublika ixtisoslashgan kardialogiya
ilmiy amaliy tibbiyot markazi Samarqand
viloyat mintaqaviy filiali direktori
(Samarqand)

Nasirova Zarina Akbarovna
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot instituti
2-sonli ichki kasalliklar kafedrasini
assistenti, PhD (mas'ul kotib)

Khalikov Kakhor Mirzayevich
Candidate of Medical Sciences,
Associate Professor, Head of the Department
of Biological Chemistry, Samarkand State
Medical University

Annaev Muzaffar
Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases and Cardiology No. 2 of the
Samarkand State Medical University
(technical secretary)

Tulabayeva Gavxar Mirakbarovna
Head of the Department of Cardiology,
Development Center professional
qualification of medical workers,
MD, professor

**Abdumadjidov Khamidulla
Amanullayevich**
"Bukhara state medical institute named
after Abu Ali ibn Sino". DSc, professor.

Saidov Maksud Arifovich
Candidate of Medical Sciences, Director
of the Samarkand Regional Department of
the Republican Specialized Scientific and
Practical Medical Center of Cardiology
(Samarkand)

Nasyrova Zarina Akbarovna
PhD, Assistant of the Department of Internal
Diseases No. 2 of the Samarkand State
Medical University (Executive Secretary)

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ЖУРНАЛ КАРДИОРЕСПИРАТОРНЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ

Хамраев Фарид Хамидуллаевич

Доцент кафедры оториноларингологии
факультета последипломного образования
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

Исмаилов Джамшид Абдураимович

PhD зав. кафедрой внутренних болезней №4
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

Расули Фаридна Орифовна

Ассистент кафедры внутренних болезней №4
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

Хамидуллаев Фирдавс Фаридович

Ассистент кафедры травматологии, ортопедии,
нейрохирургии и офтальмологии факультета
последипломного образования
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

Камалов Анвар Ибрагимович

ассистент кафедры акушерства и гинекологии
Самаркандский государственный
медицинский университет
Самарканд, Узбекистан

ИЗМЕНЕНИЕ КАЧЕСТВА ЖИЗНИ БОЛЬНЫХ С ХРОНИЧЕСКОЙ ОБСТРУКТИВНОЙ БОЛЕЗНЬЮ ЛЕГКИХ ПОСЛЕ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ БИОРЕГУЛЯТОРНЫХ ПРЕПАРАТОВ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Качество жизни (КЖ) у пациентов с хронической обструктивной болезнью легких в настоящее время является одним из основных для оценки эффективности терапии. Этот показатель напрямую связан со здоровьем, является одним из ключевых понятий современной медицины и позволяет провести глубокий анализ важных составляющих здоровья человека в соответствии с критериями ВОЗ. Все пациенты (168 человек с ХОБЛ, 90 из них с ишемической болезнью сердца) были разделены на 2 группы: основная группа (60 человек) получала базисную терапию и биорегулирующие препараты, а контрольная группа (108 человек) - только базисную терапию. КЖ оценивали с помощью опросника SF-36.

Ключевые слова: хроническая обструктивная болезнь легких, воспаление, качество жизни, биорегуляторные препараты.

Xamraev Farid Xamidullaevich

Associate Professor of the Otorhinolaryngology
Department of the Faculty of Post Graduate Education
of Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Ismailov Jamshid Abduraimovich

Head of the Department of Internal Medicine №4,
Samarkand State Medical University, PhD
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Rasuli Farida Orifovna

Assistant of the Department of Internal Medicine №4,
Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Xamidullaev Firdavs Faridovich

Assistant of the Department of Traumatology, Orthopedics,
Neurosurgery and Ophthalmology of the Faculty of Post Graduate
Education of Samarkand State Medical University
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

Kamalov Anvar Ibragimovich

assistant of department of obstetrics and gynecology
Samarkand state medical university
Samarkand, Uzbekistan

CHANGES IN THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE AFTER THE USE OF BIOREGULATORY DRUGS

ANNOTATION

The quality of life (QOL) of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease is currently one of the main indicators for assessing the effectiveness of therapy. This indicator is directly related to health, is one of the key concepts of modern medicine and allows us to carry out an in-depth analysis of important components of human health in accordance with WHO criteria. All patients (168 patients with COPD, 90 of whom had ischaemic heart disease) were divided into 2 groups: the main group (60 patients) received baseline therapy and bioregulatory drugs, and the control group (108 patients) received only baseline therapy. QOL was assessed using the SF-36 questionnaire.

Keywords: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, inflammation, quality of life, bioregulatory drugs.

Xamrayev Farid Xamidullaevich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti DKTF
Otorinolarinologiya kafedrasida dotsenti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Ismoilov Jamshid Abduraimovich

4-son ichki kasalliklar kafedrasida mudiri, PhD
Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Rasuli Farida Orifovna

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti
4-son ichki kasalliklar kafedrasida assistenti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Xamidullaev Firdavs Faridovich

Samarqand davlat tibbiyot universiteti DKTF
Traumatologiya, ortopediya kafedrasida neyroxirurgiya
va oftalmologiya assistenti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

Kamalov Anvar Ibragimovich

akusherlik va ginekologiya kafedrasida assistenti
Samarqand Davlat tibbiyot universiteti
Samarqand, O'zbekiston

BIOREGULYATSION DORILARNI QO'LLAGANIDAN KEYIN SURUNKALI OBSTRUKTIV O'PKA KASALLIGI BO'LGAN BEMORLARNING HAYOT SIFATINING O'ZGARISHI

ANNOTATSIIYA

Surunkali obstruktiv o'pka kasalligi bo'lgan bemorlarda hayot sifati (HS) hozirda terapiya samaradorligini baholash uchun asosiy hisoblanadi. Ushbu ko'rsatkich sog'liq bilan bevosita bog'liq, zamonaviy tibbiyotning asosiy tushunchalaridan biri bo'lib, JSST mezonlariga muvofiq inson salomatligining muhim tarkibiy qismlarini chuqur tahlil qilishga imkon beradi. Barcha bemorlar (168 kishi SOO'K bilan kasallangan, ulardan 90 nafari koronar arteriya kasalligi bilan) 2 guruhga bo'lingan: asosiy guruh (60 kishi) asosiy terapiya va bioregulyatsiya dori - darmonlarini, nazorat guruhi (108 kishi) esa faqat asosiy terapiyani olgan. Hayot sifati SF-36 so'rovnomasi yordamida baholandi.

Kalit so'zlar: surunkali obstruktiv o'pka kasalligi, yallig'lanish, hayot sifati, bioregulyator dorilar.

The quality of life is currently defined as an integral characteristic of a person's physical, psychological, emotional and social functioning based on their subjective perception [1]. According to the WHO definition, health is the complete physical and mental well-being of a person, not only the absence of disease. Health-related quality of life is one of the key concepts of modern medicine, allowing for a deep and multifaceted analysis of important components of human health according to WHO criteria, i.e., the physiological, psychological and social functioning of a person [2, 3]. The areas of application of QOL research in healthcare practice are quite wide. The most important are standardising treatment methods; standardising treatment methods according to international criteria applied in most developed countries; providing comprehensive individual monitoring of the patient's condition; assessing early and long-term treatment results; developing prognostic models of the course and outcome of the disease; conducting

sociomedical surveys of the population; dividing risk groups; developing basic principles of palliative care; carrying out dynamic monitoring; and assessing the effectiveness of prophylactics.

It should be noted that assessing quality of life is particularly important when reviewing new drugs or when comparing different drug regimens and treatments. In this context, QOL is an additional criterion for assessing the efficacy of drugs or treatments, as well as for performing clinical, laboratory and instrumental investigations and as a tool for assessing the side effects of investigational drugs or treatments.

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is now recognised not only as a lung disease but also as a disease with "significant extrapulmonary manifestations" (GOLD, 2014). The extrapulmonary manifestations are mainly related to the systemic inflammatory response observed in COPD patients. In the early stages of the disease, such as smoking, the inflammatory process, most commonly caused by tobacco

smoke inhalation, is localised in the bronchopulmonary tract (predominantly small airways) and may be reversible. However, over time, airway inflammation becomes persistent and widespread (in the large bronchi, lung parenchyma, and pulmonary blood vessels).

The balance between the proinflammatory and anti-inflammatory cytokine systems, the growth factors that regulate their production and interaction, and the recruitment of new immunocompetent cells to sites of inflammation determines the progression of airway obstruction from reversible to irreversible and thus determines the severity of airway obstruction. COPD affects the quality of life of patients.

The results of standard treatment for COPD can be improved by modern approaches within the framework of bioregulatory medicine, the effect of which is carried out on the body, taking into account the complex interactions of its systems. According to a number of studies, Lymphomyozot, Mucosa Compositum, the coenzyme Compositum, and Traumel C have shown good effects on respiratory diseases [6, 7]. They contain a unique combination of natural ingredients that can have complex effects on many stages of disease development. These drugs meet the requirements for modern medicines: they have a good safety profile, do not cause immunosuppression, are eliminated from the body as quickly as possible and are nontoxic.

Purpose of the present study:

To assess the quality of life of COPD patients, cytological components of sputum and bronchial lavage fluid; levels of IL-8, TNF- α , INF- γ , and IL-10 in sputum and serum; and levels of C-reactive protein, fibrinogen and serum ECE before and after baseline treatment, including modern bioregulatory drugs, were investigated.

Materials and methods

A total of 168 patients were examined, including 78 patients with COPD from different classification groups and 90 patients with a combination of CHD and COPD. All patients were divided into 2 groups—the main group (60 patients), whose patients received drugs in addition to baseline treatment for COPD; and the control group (108 patients), whose patients did not receive only baseline treatment. The mean age of the patients was 61.87 ± 10.7 years.

The diagnosis of COPD, classification groups, disease activity and background treatment were determined according to the 2014 revised criteria of the Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD, 2014).

All patients included in the study provided voluntary informed consent for clinical, instrumental and laboratory investigations. To study quality of life, a survey was conducted using the Russian version of the general questionnaire MOS-SF-36 (Medical Outcomes Study-Short Form, John E. Ware).

The MOS-SF-36 is designed for patients aged 14 years and older and is intended for use in clinical practice and research to assess the general health of the population and health strategies. The NRS-2002 consists of 36 questions covering the most important health characteristics. According to the questionnaire, the following scales are the criteria for CV: 1) "Physical functioning", 2) "Characteristics of physical functioning", 3) "Pain syndrome", 4) "General well-being", 5) "Vitality", and 6) "Vitality". Social Functioning", 7) "role emotional functioning", and 8) "mental health". The first four scales define the physical components of health. The last four scales describe the psychological components of health. The responses to the questions are expressed on a scale from 0 to 100. The scores for each scale were obtained by calculating the mean value. The higher the score is, the greater the QOL.

Patients were examined as part of the quality of life study protocol, which included questionnaires completed by the patients and clinical records completed simultaneously by the researchers.

In addition, the levels of IL-8, TNF- α , INF- γ , and IL-10 in sputum and serum were determined via enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (using Cytokine LLC kits). Serum concentrations of C-reactive protein (CRP) and fibrinogen were also measured.

A 10-week course of biomodulation therapy was administered. The protocols used were as follows: Lymphomyozot (injections): 1st injection once a week in/m during the 10th week; Mucosa Compositum (injection): 1st injection in/m once a week during the 10th week; Coenzyme Compositum (injection): 1st injection in/m during the 10th week; and Traumel C (injections) In/m.

Statistical processing of the data was performed using the program "Statistics 6.0" (StatSoft, Inc., USA). The critical value of the significance level (p) was considered to be 0.05. The data are presented as "M \pm m", where M is the arithmetic mean and m is the standard deviation.

Results of the study

According to the results of the pretreatment quality of life study, all patients in our study had a decrease in quality of life scores in the physical and emotional domains. In the questionnaire, all scale indicators decreased, especially the physical functions, physical characteristic functions, role emotional functions, social functions, strength and general health. Notably, the QOL scores in the comorbidity group were lower than those in the COPD group.

After the course of treatment, the quality of life of patients in the two groups (main and control) was compared and analysed, and it was found that in the main group, where the main treatment was supplemented with bioregulatory drugs, a significant improvement in quality of life was found on all scales characterising the superiority of physical and psychological health components. This allows patients receiving biomodulatory drugs as part of basic treatment to perform more extensive and less unpleasant everyday activities, to communicate with relatives and friends, and to increase social activity. Increased tolerance to physical stress and environmental exposure was also noted. In the group of patients who received only baseline treatment for COPD, scores on the scales "Physical function", "Pain" and "Role physical function" had only an upwards trend (did not reach the level of statistical significance), and scores of other indicators on the scales had little difference.

Changes in local and systemic inflammation have direct impacts on the dynamics of QOL in COPD patients. The accumulation of proinflammatory cytokines in tissues and bronchial secretions occurs against the background of neutrophilic inflammation, increases inflammatory manifestations, disrupts the local immune response, and damages the bronchial and lung parenchyma, which leads to the continuous progression of chronic inflammation. Moreover, it is clear that the profile characteristics of inflammatory regulators may play a significant role in the progression of lung disease, as well as in the clinical characteristics of COPD, the frequency of relapses and the rate of complications. For this reason, it is crucial to perform a thorough evaluation of cytokines with proinflammatory effects in comparison with those of the main clinical and instrumental syndromes, as well as laboratory manifestations of pulmonary pathology.

The cytological composition of bronchoalveolar fluid (sputum and bronchial lavage fluid) was studied depending on the therapy. The number of macrophages and eosinophils in sputum and bronchial lavage fluid tended to decrease in the main group receiving bioregulatory drugs. The proportion of neutrophils in sputum was markedly reduced. Similar dynamics was observed in the control group with a tendency to decrease sputum macrophages and eosinophils and simultaneous increase of these cells in bronchial flushes. Bronchial lavage also revealed a significant decrease in the neutrophil count (Table 1).

Table 1

The indicators	Main group		Control group	
	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
Macrophages (sputum)	21.6 \pm 2.2	18.7 \pm 1.9	16.9 \pm 1.4	16.88 \pm 1.1
Neutrophils (sputum)	45,1 \pm 3.1	34.6 \pm 2.3	48.1 \pm 2.7	50.2 \pm 3.2

Lymphocytes (sputum)	9,2±0.7	9.3±0.7	10.2±0.8	9.3±0.5
Eosinophils (sputum)	15.5±1.6	11.6±0.1	15.2±1.1	12±1.04
Macrophages (flushing from the bronchi)	23.8±2.6	18.5±2.0	12.6±0.8	15.5±1.3
Neutrophils (bronchial lavage)	41.6±3.01	34.7±2.2	54.1±4.0	36.8±3.6
Lymphocytes (flushing from the bronchi)	8.3±1,3	7.6±0.7	9.5±0.2	9.0±0.7
Eosinophils (bronchial washout)	10.5±1.5	7.5±0.7	8.4±0.7	14.4±1.0

Since phagocytic-active cells such as neutrophils, macrophages and immunocompetent cells—the main sources of inflammatory mediators—are attracted to the site of primary injury when inflammation persists, it is important to monitor changes in these markers during treatment. A trend toward improvement during treatment can be seen by a decrease in the number of macrophages, eosinophils and neutrophils in sputum as well as in bronchial flushes.

In addition, TNF-6, IL-8 and IL-6 are more active during the inflammatory reaction in COPD patients. The concentrations of IL-8 and TNF- α in the sputum of all patients were significantly lower ($P<0.005$) according to our analysis of the levels of proinflammatory cytokines in the BALF. The amount of sputum INF, INF and TNF- α in bronchial washings significantly decreased ($P<0.005$) in the group of patients receiving bioregulatory drugs. In bronchial smears from the control group (basic therapy), the level of IL-8 was significantly lower.

Patients in both groups initially had an increase in all the studied parameters when systemic inflammatory markers were compared before and after treatment. In both groups, there was a significant decrease in CRP (9.5-1.8 g/l before treatment and 7.6-1.5 g/l after treatment in the main group; 8.7-0.8 g/l before treatment; and 6.5-0.7 g/l after treatment in the main group). control group), TNF- α (8.8-1.7 pg/ml before treatment and 2.7-0.2 pg/ml after treatment in the main group, 5 points), and TNF- α . In the main group receiving bioregulatory drugs, there was

also a significant decrease in the ESR (18.81 mm/h before treatment and 121.6 mm/h after treatment). Thus, as COPD treatment progresses, patients gradually enter COPD remission as the level of proinflammatory cytokines in the serum decreases.

Conclusion

The statement that bioregulatory drugs have a significant impact on the quality of life of COPD patients is valid in light of the data presented. Patients noted less need for medications, as well as the disappearance or reduction of anxiety due to the absence of inhaled bronchodilators or glucocorticosteroids "at hand" as the inflammatory process and, as a consequence, somatic symptoms of the underlying disease (dyspnea, cough), pain decreased. Patients had (or developed) a more positive view of the world and themselves. They were also more likely to experience positive emotions. Considering the good tolerability and universality of drug combinations, bioregulatory drugs such as Mucosa Compositum, Trauma C, Lymphomyosot and Coenzyme Compositum seem promising for the prevention of COPD exacerbations in complex therapy. The study showed that bioregulators enhanced and complemented the anti-inflammatory effects of the main treatment, which also influenced the quality of life (QOL) of patients. Bioregulatory agents may enhance the effectiveness of existing COPD treatment plans and improve patients' quality of life.

References/Список литературы/Iqtiboslar

- Dusanovich D. A. et al. NONSPESIFIK YARALI KOLITNING KLINIK VA IMMUNOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI //JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. – Т. 7. – №. 5.
- Fazilova G. et al. The role of certain regulatory cytokines in the immunopathogenesis of extrinsic allergic alveolitis. – 2018.
- Kholliyev R. et al. The role of antioxidant enzymes in the pathogenesis of asthma and the formation of the features of its clinical course. – 2015.
- Rubenovna A. I. et al. Assessment Of The Degree Of Endothelial Dysfunction In Patients With Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Complicated By Chronic Heart Failure //Int. J. of Aquatic Science. – 2021. – Т. 12. – №. 3. – С. 2917-2922.
- Rubenovna A. I. et al. Assessment Of The Degree Of Endothelial Dysfunction In Patients With Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Complicated By Chronic Heart Failure //Int. J. of Aquatic Science. – 2021. – Т. 12. – №. 3. – С. 2917-2922.
- Rubenovna A. I. et al. DIAGNOSTIC VALUE OF IL-8 AND IL-12 IN VARIOUS FORMS OF INTERSTITIAL LUNG DISEASE //Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research. – 2022. – Т. 11. – №. 2.
- Yusufovna K. N. et al. Pharmacogenetics-A New Word in the Treatment of Rheumatoid Arthritis //Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology. – 2021. – С. 259-265.
- Ziyadullaev S. et al. The effect of budesonide on the quality of life in patients with bronchial asthma //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 1760-1766.
- Ziyadullaev S. et al. The effect of budesonide on the quality of life in patients with bronchial asthma //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 2. – С. 1760-1766.
- Зиядуллаев Ш. Х. и др. Роль некоторых регуляторных цитокинов в иммунопатогенезе экзогенных аллергических альвеолитов //Здобутки клінічної і експериментальної медицини. – 2017. – №. 1. – С. 38-41.
- Холжигитова М. Б. и др. Клиническая и бронхоскопическая характеристика воспалительного процесса у больных хроническим обструктивным бронхитом //Вопросы науки и образования. – 2019. – №. 25 (74). – С. 55-63.
- Холжигитова М. Б., Аралов Н. Р., Дусанов А. Д. Уровень факторов местного иммунитета при хроническом обструктивном бронхите у лиц подросткового возраста //Тюменский медицинский журнал. – 2016. – Т. 18. – №. 1. – С. 52-55.

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Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000